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ASPECTS
aspects-quantum.com

ASPECTS Dissemination, Exploitation, and Communication Plan

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Table of Contents

1. Introduction	3
2. Dissemination, communication and exploitation activities	3
2.1. Dissemination of scientific output	3
2.2. Communication	5
2.3. Exploitation	6
2.4. Expected impact	7
2.5. ASPECTS Meetings & Workshops	9
3. Internal management and reporting of DEC	10
3.1 Internal reporting	10
3.2 Progress monitoring	11
4. Visual identity for ASPECTS	11

1. Introduction

This document details the plan for dissemination, exploitation and communication DEC of results for the EU-funded project “Quantum Thermodynamics of Precision in Electronic Devices” (ASPECTS, Grant Agreement No. 101080167). ASPECTS is a fundamental science project, whose main objective is to exploit quantum coherent processes occurring in nanoscale circuit devices to obtain a thermodynamic advantage for precision measurement. The project aims to make a deep and lasting impact on the European research landscape by:

- ▲ pushing the boundaries of scientific understanding through ground-breaking experiments
- ▲ training a network of experts at the intersection of quantum metrology and thermodynamics
- ▲ fostering connections between the Consortium, the Quantum Flagship, and key industrial actors
- ▲ developing educational materials for schools and universities
- ▲ informing and educating the population through public outreach

DEC forms an integral part of all of the above objectives, and this document describes the various different DEC measures by which ASPECTS will achieve its goals.

In preparing this plan, we have followed guidance from the European Commission as well as from the SFI centre for Advanced Materials and BioEngineering Research (AMBER) at Trinity College Dublin. It is important to note that this DEC plan is a “living document”, which will evolve as the project progresses.

2. Dissemination, communication and exploitation activities

2.1. Dissemination of scientific output

The primary scientific output will be peer-reviewed publications in high-profile journals (PRL, PRX, Nature Phys., Quantum, etc.) with more technical results published in society journals (PRA, PRB, PRE,

NJP, etc.). All papers will be permanently deposited on the open-access archives arXiv.org and TARA. Key results will be presented through talks at international conferences, including Quantum Flagship meetings, major series such as Quantum Information Processing (QIP), APS March Meeting, Quantum ThermoDynamics (QTD), etc. and smaller topical conferences as and when they arise throughout the duration of the project. Tensor-network code developed for WP1 will be made publicly available by depositing it on the open-access GitHub repository. Data and software necessary for scientific reproducibility will also be made open-access through GitHub, arXiv, and/or the open-access repository Zenodo. See the ASPECTS Data Management Plan (DMP) for full details of our strategy for ensuring that all scientific data and software are findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable (FAIR).

We will organise a scientific workshop targeted at the Quantum Flagship in the third year of the project. The workshop will bring together other researchers working under the Quantum Flagship programme to discuss the current status and future prospects for European research on energy-efficient quantum technologies. This will help to connect and integrate ASPECTS within the broader Flagship activities. We will aim to achieve gender balance – with a minimum of 30% women across organisers, chairs and speakers – and will give special consideration to individuals from underrepresented groups within physics, such as the disabled, persons of colour, and the LGBTQ+ community. One day of the workshop will be devoted to an inclusive Careers Day, discussing topics such as standard and non-standard career paths within academia; work-life balance including childcare, mobility requirements and other issues disproportionately affecting female scientists; and a half-day session with invited talks given by speakers from the quantum private sector. This will not only provide useful information for researchers starting their careers – especially those in marginalised groups – but will also contribute to the industrial impact of ASPECTS by fostering connections between early-career researchers and industry. The UM partner will continue their organisation of the existing conference series New Trends in Complex Quantum System Dynamics, which will also include a Careers Day. This will provide further opportunities to disseminate the results of ASPECTS to the quantum physics community.

Finally, our new Hop-on grant ENACT will fund extra dissemination activities. University of Malta (UoM) will organise a Summer School in Malta modeled on the successful format of QALYPSO22 “Quantum Computation and Open Quantum Systems”, attended by 80+ students, by ASPECTS consortium members as well as by quantum technology companies (IBM, Quantinuum) and Maltese institutional and economic stakeholders, e.g., MITA-Malta Information Technology Agency and Malta Enterprise. The target audience for the Summer School QALYPSO23 “Quantum Thermodynamics and Quantum Technologies” will be 100+ students, with students aid grants for gender balance, underrepresented groups and widening countries students. QALYPSO23 constitutes a relevant added value to ASPECTS as it will provide access to new talent pools and improve knowledge circulation between the consortium members and Malta. Participation of UoM researchers at conferences planned by ASPECTS and joint publications in high-profile peer-reviewed journals will be implemented in the dissemination measures of ENACT and integrated into ASPECTS.

Website and social media presence. – To further promote our progress, we have published a website dedicated to the project (www.aspects-quantum.com). This includes a description of the scientific aims, details of the consortium members, and news updates on major events such as scientific publications, conferences, and so on. A dedicated Twitter profile for the consortium has already been established (https://twitter.com/ASPECTS_quantum) which makes weekly posts or reposts about quantum technologies, highlighting news about the Quantum Flagship, and posts monthly progress updates for the ASPECTS project. Both the website and the Twitter profile will help to publicise our

results to the scientific community and the wider public, as well as acting as a permanent digital record of the project's progress.

2.2. Communication

Besides the scientific dissemination measures, the results of the project will be also communicated to audiences outside academia. A comprehensive set of communication activities (outlined in Table 1) will be developed to inform, engage, and create awareness and promote information about the project's objectives and its outputs. To this end, the Media Relations Teams of each partner's institution will play a major role in supporting the communication of the research activities. The communication activities within ASPECTS project are set up for the following main reasons:

- ▲ To reach public and private stakeholders dealing with innovation and willing to collaborate at international level in a common European innovation ecosystem.
- ▲ To show how the collaboration between different regional innovation ecosystems from different EU countries and the UK has achieved more in promoting innovation and solving scaling issues compared to working separately.
- ▲ To present how the outcomes of the project can be relevant not only at regional level but also at European level.
- ▲ To improve connectedness between start-ups, large corporations, investors, and academia across the EU.
- ▲ To promote understanding and awareness among students and the general public about quantum technologies and their importance for a sustainable digital economy in Europe.

Industrial entities.– Quantum technology is a dynamic industrial landscape populated with many start-ups, often founded as spin-offs from academia, and ASPECTS will aim to emulate this pattern for commercial success. The collaboration in recent years between the UM representative, Prof. Prior, and the Zakut innovation hub will allow us to connect with entrepreneurs and venture capitalists and accelerate the generation of patentable IP and spin-offs. Zakut will introduce consortium partners to companies with interest in high tech applications. They will also provide economic and business training on IP management, and coach members of the research team on the creation of start-up companies. We will also target Regional Innovation Networks – local communities of entrepreneurs – in each of the partners' countries to broaden our network.

The two main group of industrial stakeholders, entrepreneurs/start-ups and large corporations identified above will be addressed with the following targeted communication measures:

- ▲ The organisation of a hackathon for quantum start-ups and small-medium sized enterprises (SMEs), where at least 5 corporations (not necessarily in the quantum sector) will set challenges for the start-ups/ SMEs to solve together with the different ASPECTS partners.
- ▲ Regional Innovation Networks (RINs) at each partner's location will be targeted through the EU Virtual Platform and via "innovation breakfast" meetings with RIN members and academia.
- ▲ We will hold a quantum industry forum for corporations, investors and procurers at TCD, aimed at facilitating communication between academics working under the Quantum Flagship and the private sector in the Dublin area.

General public.–We will target the general public program with a balanced outreach programme, including:

- ▲ Public engagement workshop: a citizens' half-day "think-in" event will be held with adults and young people to facilitate two-way dialogue on quantum technology research and its societal impacts. The events will be linked to the website and social media channels. Videos of these

workshops will be posted on social media (given GDPR restrictions). We will develop and run this with the AMBER EPE team.

- ▲ Educational materials (videos, lesson plans) based on our research, produced together with the AMBER EPE team.
- ▲ Press releases about important research results, which will be pushed to a broad news audience with the help of the partners' Media Relations Teams.
- ▲ Long-form articles written for specialised newspapers such as [The Conversation](#).
- ▲ General talks in schools about quantum science and technology, targeted particularly at girls' schools and those in underprivileged areas, in order to promote STEM subjects to underrepresented groups.
- ▲ Participation by each partner in local outreach initiatives including Science Week, Pint of Science, the annual MSCA funded Researchers Night, etc.

ENACT will complement ASPECTS Communication activities outlined above by primarily focusing on the Maltese quantum ecosystem. It will spearhead the participation of Maltese stakeholders in the planned quantum industry forum, the hackathon, and integrate with the Regional Innovation Networks (RINs) at the consortium's partners locations by identifying, outside the academia, relevant national start-ups and SMEs. More specifically, in order to kickstart a Green Deal compatible EuroQCI, UoM will organise two international panel discussion bringing together national stakeholders, e.g., MITA, Malta Enterprise, MEFL (Ministry responsible for the implementation of a Digital Economy for Malta) and EU representatives, from team leaders of relevant Flagship projects to representatives of DG CONNECT, Directorate-General Communications Networks, Content and Technology, responsible for the EuroQCI implementation. These activities will boost Malta's visibility at the highest scientific and institutional level.

2.3. Exploitation

Opportunities for exploitation.—The results of ASPECTS have significant commercialisation potential that we will capture with appropriate exploitation measures. In particular, we expect that our demonstration of quantum-thermodynamic precision advantage (QTPA) in a measuring device will lead to patentable IP. We will also consider the creation of a spin-off company to further develop and exploit this IP into a commercial product.

Intermediate technological advances made in the pursuit the of objectives such as to build autonomous quantum clocks with nanoelectromechanical systems and circuit quantum electrodynamics devices and measure the energetic cost of timekeeping in the quantum domain, to construct two apparatuses to measure the state of a quantum bit using thermal noise, and to implement the first proof-of-principle demonstration of a quantum-thermodynamic precision advantage, may also lead to saleable patents. For example, improved techniques for measuring heat currents and fluctuations in superconducting qubits could be of commercial value for small- and medium-sized enterprise or large corporations with an interest in noisy intermediate-scale quantum hardware, where heat dissipation remains a limiting factor.

Management of intellectual property.—In order to manage the IP arising from the project, the following matters will be outlined and agreed in a Consortium Agreement prior to the signing of the Grant Agreement: the background IP for each participant; confidentiality rules; rules for the protection, dissemination and exploitation of results; publication rights and minimum notification period. In accordance with the Horizon Europe GA, results arising from this project will rest with the beneficiary that created them. To avoid or resolve any ownership disputes, beneficiaries will keep detailed documentation of research activities to show how and when the results were produced.

During the project, IP will be managed strategically by the ASPECTS management board, with Prof. Prior (UM) assigned as IP manager. The board will meet every 3 months to review results, identify potential publication and exploitation opportunities, and handle decisions on interpretations of Consortium Agreement rules. A review of IP, protection and commercialisation measures will be coordinated with the assistance of the dedicated TCD Technology Transfer Office (TTO) ICT Case Manager.

When engaging with third parties, the TTO and project coordinator shall ensure the appropriate non-confidentiality agreements are concluded to ensure IP protection. Researchers will receive training in IPR and data management from our industrial collaborator Zakut. In order to maximise the project's impact, researchers will have the right to publish their research results, subject to the terms of the Consortium Agreement and following consultation with TTCM with regard to protecting IP where needed. The local Technology Transfer Office of each partner will assist the consortium in the identification, protection and exploitation of IP arising from their respective research activities.

2.4. Expected impact

In order to maximise the impact of dissemination, communication, and exploitation, specific measures will be adopted. These measures, as outlined in Table 1, aim to enhance the effectiveness of dissemination, communication, and exploitation efforts. Each DEC activity is targeted at a specific subgroup from the stakeholders described in Sec. 2.2, and each is assigned a target impact metric against which its success will be quantitatively assessed.

Table 1. Planned DEC activities of ASPECTS

Target group	DEC activity	Objective of engagement	Target impact metric	Location/frequency
Research community	Peer-reviewed articles in high-impact and open-access journals	Disseminate scientific results	Min. 10 articles published	Nature research journals (Nature, Nat. Phys), APS journals (PRX, PRL, PRA, PRB), IOP journals (NJP), Quantum, SciPost...
	Conference presentation	Disseminate scientific results	Min. 10 conferences attended per year by consortium members	Quantum Flagship meetings, QIP, APS March Meeting, Quantum ThermoDynamics (QTD), other major series
	ASPECTS website	Promote ASPECTS, record progress	Min. 30 website hits per month	Ongoing throughout the project
	Twitter account	Promote ASPECTS, record progress	Min. 500 followers by end of the project	At least one post/repost per week

	Seminars and research visits	2-way knowledge transfer	Min. 10 seminars per year for the entire consortium	Group seminars around the world
	Flagship scientific workshop	Integrate ASPECTS within the Quantum Flagship; disseminate results	Min. 50 conference attendees	In second year of ASPECTS
Junior scientists, students	Career Days	Inform and include marginalised groups	Min. 30 attendees; min. 10 feedback surveys returned by attendees after 2 years	Sessions held during scientific workshops
	MSc module	Educate; engage with topic of ASPECTS	Min. 15 students pass module	Taught at TCD in final academic year of ASPECTS
	Summer School (QALYPSO23)	Provide access to new talent pools; improve knowledge circulation between the consortium members and Malta	Min. 100 students	To be held in Malta in 2023
Corporations	Industry forum	Connect Dublin corporations with Quantum Flagship researchers	Min. 8 corporations represented	1 event at TCD
SMEs & entrepreneurs	Innovation breakfasts; hackathon	Connect with entrepreneurs and SMEs	Min. 12 SMEs represented per event	Innovation breakfasts: 1 event at each partner country Hackathon: 1 event at TCD

General public	Press releases and articles	Educate public about quantum technologies	At least one national news article per year	On publication of key results
	“Think-in” workshop	Encourage public participation in scientific process	Min. 50 participants	1 event at TCD
	Science Week, Researchers Night etc.	Educate and entertain public	Min. 1 event per year per partner	In each partner country throughout the year
School children & teachers	Educational materials	Introduce children to STEM; enhance teachers’ repertoire	Min. 100 downloads after two years	Released at end of project
	School talks	Inform and engage schoolchildren (esp. girls, marginalised groups) with STEM	Min. 1 talk per year by each partner	Primary and secondary schools in partner countries

2.5. Scientific meetings & workshops

Several scientific meetings and workshops/conferences are planned during the lifetime of ASPECTS. These meetings will foster collaboration among ASPECTS staff and PhD students, cement positive working relationships, and instigate the transfer of knowledge and ideas between the nodes of the consortium and with external parties. Table 2 details these events and their planned dates and locations.

Table 2. Meetings planned during the lifetime of ASPECTS

Event title	Event description	Location	Timing	Lead organisers
Initial PI meeting	First in-person meeting of ASPECTS PIs, to discuss organisational strategies and establish a common scientific vision	Vienna	1-5 August 2022	TUW
Kick-off meeting	First in-person meeting of consortium staff: Introduction to goals and procedures of ASPECTS from the Coordinator	Murcia	12-15 June 2023 (M8)	TCD, UM

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ⚠ Topical tutorials from postdocs ⚠ Research updates from PhD students 			
Consortium meeting	Second in-person consortium meeting: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ⚠ Progress summary from each partner ⚠ Develop working relationships with staff at new ENACT partner UoM ⚠ Establish working groups for the second phase of the project 	Malta	March 2024 (M17)	TCD, UoM
QALYPSO24	Summer school entitled "Quantum Thermodynamics and Quantum Technologies", aimed at students and postdocs both internal and external to ASPECTS	Malta	September 2024 (M23)	UoM
Final consortium meeting	Third in-person consortium meeting: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ⚠ Progress summary from each partner ⚠ Establish roadmap for extending project's impact beyond its funding lifetime, including exploitation measures and acquisition of further funding 	Dublin	May 2025 (M31)	TCD
Quantum Flagship workshop	Scientific conference on energy-efficient quantum technologies, aimed at bringing quantum thermodynamics research into the mainstream of the Quantum Flagship	Dublin	October 2025 (M36)	TCD

3. Internal management and reporting of DEC

3.1 Internal reporting

All consortium members will record their DEC activities using an internally shared spreadsheet, with the format shown in Table 3. This continuous internal reporting ensures that all DEC activities conducted by the consortium, including the associated impact metrics, are recorded in the final version of the DEC plan, which will be submitted at the end of the project.

Table 3. Template spreadsheet for internal reporting of DEC activities

Researcher name	Affiliation	Type	Title	Venue/ Journal ref.	DOI/ link	Date	#Participants (if relevant for impact metric)
	[TCD]	[Journal article]					
	[TUW]	[Preprint]					
	[CUT]	[Conference talk]					
	[UM]						

	[UO] [UoM]	[Conference poster] [Seminar] [Public event] [School talk] [Press article] [Social media post] [*add more options as needed]					
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3.2 Progress monitoring

In order to ensure that ASPECTS achieves its DEC goals, several more junior staff members have been appointed to monitor and coordinate activities within the consortium:

- ▲ The DEC Reporting Officer (Dr. Aamir Ali, CUT) monitors the progress of DEC activities and ensures that consortium members report activities in a timely fashion
- ▲ The Industrial Engagement Officer (Dr. Federico Fedele, UO) coordinates industrial engagement activities and be responsible for liaising with industrial contacts
- ▲ The Data Management Officer (Dr. Saulo Moreira, TCD) ensures that data management procedures, as outlined in the ASPECTS Data Management Plan, are followed by consortium members
- ▲ The Digital Communications Officer (Ms. Khalak Mahadeviya, TCD) is in charge of maintaining and updating the project website and Twitter account

Each of these officers will provide informal progress reports every 2 months to the Coordinator. These progress reports will be discussed at the regular consortium meetings between ASPECTS PIs. Each PI will have responsibility of ensuring that DEC targets at their own institution are met, with the Coordinator maintaining overall oversight and responsibility of DEC within the consortium.

4. Visual identity for ASPECTS

We have developed a visual identity for ASPECTS, which will be used consistently across our website, online communications, conference presentations, project deliverables, etc. This consistency will establish a recognisable "brand" for the consortium that will assist effective communication with scientific peers and the general public. Figs. 1-3 below showcase this visual identity.

Figure 1. ASPECTS logo in black (left) or green (right). Used to acknowledge the consortium on websites, talk slides, posters etc.

Figure 2. Thumbnail graphics, which can be used together with the logo in Fig. 1, or in isolation for small-scale graphics, e.g. document headers or bullet points, clickable buttons on websites, etc.

Figure 3. Digital artwork representing the project's scientific objectives, which merge the science of measurement (scales) with thermodynamics (flame) in the quantum regime (atom)